

CATALISI

Catalysation of institutional transformations
of Higher Education Institutions through
the adoption of acceleration services

DELIVERABLE 3.1 COORDINATION AND DEFINITION OF COUNSELING SERVICE 31/03/2023.

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DELIVERABLE 3.1 COORDINATION AND DEFINITION OF COUNSELING SERVICE

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The report aims at defining the framework of the counseling service which will be performed by Ernst & Young, one of the 11 partners of CATALISI project. The counseling service will be implemented within the project CATALISI, for the catalysation of institutional transformations of Higher Education Institutions through the adoption of acceleration services. In particular, the report makes reference to the whole process for the fulfilment of the counseling service which is connected to different tasks of the project and whose contributors are 10 partners.

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Summaries are useful for people who have neither the time nor the inclination to read a lengthy document but who want to scan the primary points quickly and then decide whether they need to read the entire version.

A summary should be short enough to be economical and long enough to be clear and comprehensive. Don't sacrifice meaning for brevity. A short, confusing summary will take more of a busy executive's time than a somewhat longer but clear one.

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ABBREVIATIONS

AUTH	University of Thessaloniki-Greece
CoP	Community of Practice
ENoLL	European Network of Living Labs
EY	Ernst & Young
HEI	Higher Education Institution
KTU	Kaunas University of Technology
LUISS	Libera Università Internazionale degli Studi Sociali Guido Carli
UCC	University College Cork
UG	University of Gdansk
UJI	University Jaume I
VUMC	University Medical Centers

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 INTRODUCTION TO CATALISI

The European Commission has outlined Institutional Change as a key strategy to address the challenges of **Responsible Research Innovation (RRI)**. Governing and driving the transformations affecting science and innovation as well as their positive and negative implications require, to a certain extent, the implementation of institutional changes in research organizations. The challenges that Higher Education Institutions face concern not only bridging the gap between the HEIs disparities in terms of R&I performance but also building a R&I system where **Higher Education Institutions (HEIs)** in Europe can navigate and cooperate in the production and dissemination of high-quality knowledge. On this note, the European project **CATALISI** aims at helping and supporting HEIs to successfully implement a strategy and individual pathways for institutional transformation through the adoption of acceleration services. In particular, CATALISI will analyse how the **governance of HEIs** can be changed, considering governance as a way in which societal and state actors intentionally interact to transform science technology and innovation systems, by regulating issues of societal concern. The project is shaped and developed around two intertwining dimensions that will be implemented by each HEI (**implementers**), with the support of experienced facilitators. CATALISI has identified three domains (Research Careers and Talent Support, Research Modus Operandi, and Sustainable Financing Schemes) which include different intervention areas that refer to specific institutional transformation needs that could be deemed necessary by each HEI.

1.2 TASK 3.1 – COORDINATION AND DEFINITION OF THE COUNSELING SERVICE

The counseling service, is a task that aims at building ad hoc transformational pathways for each HEI to support the acceleration of institutional transformation and will be designed, implemented and monitored by Ernst & Young (EY). It will be a **cross-cutting** service that will be available throughout the duration of the project for implementers (HEIs) to access based on their identified needs. The service will cover all the intervention areas and will create a framework to evaluate and collect needs from each HEI. This, will allow EY to better match the demand and the offer of each university involved in the project as beneficiary.

Specifically, this task will:

- Define the role of the counselor who will act as a bridge between HEIs and experts in specific domains
- Design approaches to implement the counseling service on the basis of HEIs needs
- Build a framework to guide and support each HEI in pursuing their objectives in the field.

2. THE COUNSELING SERVICE

2.1 INTRODUCTION TO THE COUNSELING SERVICE

EY CATALISI Team will coordinate, design and implement the counseling service starting by M3. The service will be performed in parallel to HEIs' needs analysis which will be conducted as per tasks included in Work Package 1 "*Acting LL co-creation*". In particular, there are two tasks in Work Package 1, which will be carried out by ENoLL (European Network of Living Labs) and that will serve as baseline for the counseling service.

The tasks are:

- *Task 1.1 "Setting up the CATALISI Acting-Living Labs"*: This task entails the development of a stakeholder mapping. Key actors will be identified along the complete value chain, outlining their responsibilities and influences, mapping them into a 4-helix model. The HEIs will initiate the process through their network and established connections with guidance, coordination and facilitation of ENoLL and AUTH (University of Thessaloniki-Greece)
- *Task 1.2 "CATALISI Living Lab: Exploration Stage"*: The second task includes the mapping of the values, concerns, needs and expectations of the identified 4-helix stakeholders. To do so, a series of qualitative participatory techniques will be applied: in-depth interviews, surveys based on qualitative questionnaires and one workshop per HEI.

Data collected during *Task 1.2* will be used for the building of a transformational pathway for each HEI, which will be set out by M8.

Between M3 and M8, the counseling service will be carried out by EY CATALISI Team, on the basis of the needs' analysis executed in Work Package 1 and after providing a first version of transformational pathways as per Work Package 3, *Task 3.2 "Design lab for transformational pathway: strategy and agenda setting"*.

The counseling service will be carried out by a **facilitator** - represented by EY - for the HEIs involved in the project as beneficiaries. The counselling service will include **mentoring** and **coaching**, meaning that each implementer will be able to refer to either a **mentor** or a **coach** in case of need and support throughout the execution of CATALISI. On the one hand, the **mentor** (facilitator) will provide guidance based on their own experiences and according to each **transformational path** (of the implementer). On the other hand, the **coach** (facilitator) will give more focused guidance on specific problems, solvable in short period of time, such as **skills' equipment** for a specific situation. The HEIs that will benefit from the service are defined **implementers**. The services provided can be understood as standby ones, meaning that each HEI will be able to access in case of need and support throughout the execution of the project. Within this framework, the facilitator enables meaningful and useful exchange between the HEI and selected experts from the *Community of Practice*. The *Community of Practice* will be involved in CATALISI activities in order to maximise the impact of the results. The experts will be selected through a "call for experts" (as per *Task 6.3 "Coordination and animation of the Community of Practice"*) starting from M1 and their network will be involved

in Work Package 1, 2, 3, 4 activities. The experts for the HEIs will be chosen by the facilitator. They can be recruited both from the *Community of Practice* and from the implementing HEIs.

The main role of the counseling services is to infuse perspective and stewardship when difficulties arise in the pursuit of institutional transformation, by conveying its knowledge to the situation regarded as challenging. Moreover, the counseling service is designed as a **cross-cutting service** to all other acceleration services as it gives constant and accessible guidance throughout the duration of the whole project for all HEIs involved.

FIGURE 1 - IMPLEMENTATION OF THE COUNSELING SERVICE (ACCORDING TO WORK PACKAGES)

2.2 WHO WILL BENEFIT FROM THE SERVICE?

CATALISI will be carried out by a consortium integrating 11 partners from 8 EU member states, covering different geographical areas of Europe. Among those, 7 HEIs (**implementers**) will be able to benefit from the counseling service performed by the EY CATALISI Team. While accessing and implementing the acceleration services, some implementers themselves will have the possibility to be considered as "**frontrunners**" in the intervention areas that they have acquired expertise in. The HEIs which do not have expertise in specific intervention areas will be considered as "**followers**" (Table 2).

HEIs involved are:

- Kaunas University of Technology (**KTU**) – Lithuania
- University Jaume I (**UJI**) – Spain
- Libera Università Internazionale degli Studi Sociali Guido Carli (**LUISS**) – Italy
- University of Gdansk (**UG**)– Poland
- University College Cork (**UCC**) – Ireland
- University of Thessaloniki (**AUTH**) – Greece
- Stichting VUMC (**VUMC**)– Netherlands

HEIs will benefit from the counseling service performed by EY CATALISI team, through constant guidance and support provided by EY CATALISI Team. On this note, EY will contribute to accelerate HEIs' institutional transformation by facilitating the implementation of the counseling service and more importantly by matching HEIs' needs with the activities proposed.

TABLE 1 - CONTENT OF SPECIFIC INSTITUTIONAL TRANSFORMATIONS

Domains	Intervention area	AUTH	KTU	UCC	UG	UJI	LUISS	VUMC
Research Careers & Talent Support	Recognition of qualifications and research careers	X		O	O	X		X
	Reform of research assessment	X	X	O	O	X	O	X
	Digitisation of higher education sector	X	O		O			
	Supporting talent circulation/mobility	X	X	O	X		X	
	Accurately addressing lifelong learning	O			O			
	Strengthening of human capital	O	X		O			
	Gender equality and inclusiveness	X	O	O	O	X		O
Research Modus Operandi	Mainstreaming of open science and digitisation of research	O	O		O	X	X	O
	Public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social	X	X	O	X	X	X	
	Reinforcing the role of universities in local innovation ecosystems	O	X	X	O			
	Sharing of research infrastructure and capacities	X		X	O			
Sustainable Financing Schemes	Sustainability in education	X	X		O			
	Sustainability in research	X	X	X	O		X	O
	Sustainability in campus operations	O			X			

Table 2 "X" represents the areas in which the implementers carry out institutional transformations, "O" the areas in which they contribute to the acceleration services with their own expertise

*Table 2 is not to be considered as final since it will be finalised after a workshop in April 2023

2.3 ROLE OF THE FACILITATOR: WHO IS THE FACILITATOR?

The facilitator is a key figure in the institutional transformation process. EY will act as a facilitator for the counseling service, enabling the connection between HEIs and experts who will help them tackle the most challenging issues. According to literature review, facilitators are pivotal for the success of the counseling service. On this note, facilitators will provide access to relevant resources and continuous feedback. This, with the aim of supporting the acceleration of the institutional transformation in the most effective way and providing guidance to HEIs during the whole project duration.

3. FRAMEWORK OF THE COUNSELING SERVICE

3.1 INTRODUCTION – THE CREATION OF THE FRAMEWORK

The framework of the counseling service has been created based on EY recognized competence in strategic consulting, coaching and education, as well as on the challenges highlighted during the co-creative event. On the account of literature review, there is an increased need for counseling services for HEIs. On this note, counseling becomes crucial since it has been generally defined as the process of assisting HEIs to better understand themselves, discover their interests, and maximize their capacities in achieving their goals (*International Journal of Education, 2019*). The key take-aways of the co-creative event made it clear that a structure is needed to identify HEIs which need expertise and those which can provide it. Therefore, the framework has been structured in a way that allows to build a **customised service** that takes into account the different needs of each HEI and that keeps monitoring the implementation of the activities proposed.

3.1.1 Cycle of the counseling service

The counseling service has been designed as an **iterative cycle**, with the aim of monitoring all the phases of the counseling service and ensure a **flexible structure** that can be changed according to each HEI's needs. The timing is featured by **periodical meetings** between the experts and HEIs with the aim of checking in on the status of the activities. The service will be implemented according to **4 phases**. The **1st phase** includes the development of a 1st version of transformational pathways for each HEI, as per *Task 3.2 Design lab for transformational pathway: strategy and agenda setting*. The pathway will consist of a **"living document"** which will be updated or adjusted on the basis of the output of each activity. The expert will play a key role in the whole process and will provide guidance to HEIs by having regular meetings and getting feedback from them. On the account of those meetings, the facilitator will modify and include other activities in a final report.

FIGURE 2 - PHASES OF THE COUNSELING SERVICE

The task phases are the following:

1. After data is collected during *Tasks 1.2, 2.2* and *3.2*, a 1st version of **transformational pathways** is developed.
2. EY will facilitate the **matching** between HEIs and experts. This, in case HEIs will make a request for counseling service to be performed by experts recruited from the *Community of Practice* or from implementing HEIs
3. Experts will test and evaluate the implementation of the activities proposed by having one-to-one interviews with HEIs. The interviews will take place on a **3-month basis** and **on-demand** if deemed necessary by HEIs. The questions that will be asked are:
 - o *What are the challenges of your institution related to the intervention areas? How do they impact on the institutional transformation?*
 - o *Which opportunities do you see as ways of improving your performance in the domains?*
 - o *(From the 2nd meeting onwards) Do you think that the activities suggested are positively impacting your institutional transformation? If yes, what has helped? If not, why not?*
4. EY CATALISI Team will change the **pre-defined transformational pathways** in case the activities proposed are not effective and HEIs are willing to include different activities. This will be done on the basis of the feedback collected from the experts during phase no.3

3.1.2 Activities proposed by the Counseling Service

The counseling service entails the design and the facilitation of several activities that will be proposed by EY. EY will propose tailor-made activities on the basis of each HEIs' requests and needs that also align with those included in *Work Package 1 "Acting LLS Co-creation"*, *Work Package 3 "Design, Coaching and Sustainability"* and *Work Package 6 "Project Management"*. This, with the goal of building a framework which is consistent with the other CATALISI activities and which support Higher Education Institutions to successfully implement a long-term strategy and individual pathway for institutional transformation through the adoption of acceleration services.

TABLE 2 - ACTIVITIES PROPOSED BY THE COUNSELING SERVICE

Activity	Description
Twinning Activities	EY will support the planning of a twinning programme as outlined in Work Package 2.4, in order to secure the knowledge shared among the implementers and experienced on how other implementers (peers) have already performed specific institutional changes
Thematic Workshops	EY will support the organization of thematic workshops for knowledge-sharing of best practices. Workshops are part of the activities included in Work Package 2 – Task 2.4 "Multi level knowledge transfer among the implementers"

Webinars	EY will advise HEIs on which webinar to attend through the Learning Hub platform. Webinars will be organised through the Learning Hub platform, as outlined in Work Package 2- Task 2.1 "Setting up the learning hub". The advice will be on the intervention areas which is of most interest to them.
Awareness activities	EY will support the organisation of awareness activities, as outlined in Work Package 5 – Task 5.2 "Communication & Awareness activities"
Marketplace	EY will support each HEIs on identifying potential opportunities in the marketplace which will be developed in Work Package 3 – Task 3.4 "Market Place: Support to Sustainable funding"
One-to-one meetings	EY will support the organization of «peer-to-peer» meetings between HEIs which hold expertise in specific domains and HEIs which lack expertise of those specific areas. This activity will be implemented in case the other activities do not contribute achieving the desired goals set out by each HEI.

4. CONCLUSION

The purpose of the report is to build a framework for the whole project duration and it will be used as guideline for the execution of the counseling service. The framework will be subject to change on the basis of each HEI's experience, feedback and output of pathways suggested.

This report has shown the different activities that can be implemented during the HEIs transformational pathway. The activities will be proposed according to the feedback collected by EY, resulting from **one-to-one interviews between experts** and HEIs. The whole process will be supported and monitored by the **facilitator**, a key figure who enables the connection between HEIs and the experts who significantly will contribute to the transformational pathways of each HEI. The consortia can also count on EY Wavespace that is EY's collective intelligence centre. The centre allows the generation of transformative experiences, the organisation of immersive training sessions, research labs, and institutional events, thanks to interconnected spaces and innovative technologies.

The next task of the project will be *Task 3.2: Design lab for transformational pathway: strategy and agenda setting*. This task will focus on the development and tailoring of the transformational pathways to the specific institutional needs of the **implementers (HEIs)**. The roadmap framework will be developed based on the results outcomes carried out in Work Package 1. It will be structured to assure the definition and achievement of a series of short-term (during the project timespan) goals that will provide the basis for a medium- and long-term sustainable institutional changes rewarding. EY will coordinate the design of a set of well-defined **intervention areas** in the three different **domains** and a first version of these documents will be provided by **M8**. Being transformational pathways a living document during the project, it will be revised twice: in M24 and at the end of the project, M36.

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